

>><https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=x2PxBY0vFTQ>
>><https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1A6ikRgZBf8>
>><https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=50loQwB-WwU>

Strong Letter Response to Mr. Ben Davidson, Suspicious Observers, et al.

Standing in support of mainstream skeptics and altstream EU, PU, MU, and NASA/ESA scientists by utilizing EPEMC peer-review standards and code of conduct and ethics.

(Best Viewed at: <https://bit.ly/3hSKUvc>)

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September 21, 2021

Re: The Micronova and Moving Through the Galactic Sheet

From the Desk of Sf. Ramon Careaga, founder EPEMC, sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway

Dear Readers,

I have given tacit support¹ for Mr. Davidson for over five years. In general he seems to focus upon the “sharp edge of the razor” in climate science, biology, astronomy, and *electrogeology*. However, since the introduction of the micronova falsified hypothesis, and misinterpretation of Younger Dryas Event² data, in order to frighten people, push a narrative, betray colleagues at the Thunderbolts Project³ (whom I am in no way affiliated with), mute people who disagree with him⁴, and operate in all the ways that indicate a cult-like leadership,

¹ Monetarily, buying books, watching videos, and providing good counsel regarding his electroquake experiment (and subsequent failure, statistically speaking), and improvements to the Disaster Prediction App.

² <https://www.britannica.com/science/Younger-Dryas-climate-interval>

³ I was a long time subscriber and saw his “Deeper Look” video which made heinous accusations of fraud, scamming, pseudoscience, and “satanism” of all things, about the TBP. I also saw him make a play on stage at EU2018 and try to force an aging David Talbott to sell to him or name him as the public “best choice” of successor. It was embarrassingly overt and full of impropriety.

⁴ He muted me, for example, for asking him “Ben, how’s your energy?” after he was attacking his own YouTube followers with abusive language.

including attacking people as less intelligent, even after they say they are long term supporters.

Figure 1 - Mocking supporters? Credit: Ben Davidson⁵, Suspicious Observers

I was also disgusted by his way of essentially professional doxxing a scientist at NASA, calling her “NASA’s very own Karen⁶”, ostensibly to foment anger towards her and “lob zombies” of cult followers at her, misrepresenting the altstream, plasma cosmologists, Dr. Peratt⁷, and PEMC in general. His ego has become out of control, which is typical of social media influencers.

But the most egregious amount of fear mongering⁸ without de facto proof, is claiming to predict the future with a small number of data points, and a strong suspicion [which is not entirely off base], but is nevertheless a form of a *priori* knowledge. That is to say, **pseudoscience**.

Given that we know the Earth turned over in the last 7,000 years, based on mathematically sound data from the Jovian Octagons vs. 3 sites of Hopewell Earthworks⁹, and the implications, and that we have the testimony of the myths in “Enki & the World Order,”^{10 11}

⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lr4uoyd-WaE>

⁶ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yWFXlsxZxNM>

⁷ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/pu-research/peratt>

⁸ While claiming “eyes open, no fear.” Reminds me of Google’s “don’t be evil.”

⁹

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332316290_Hopewellian_Octagons_Proof_that_the_Allegewi_Astronomers_could_see_Jupiter_up_close_Analysis_of_the_Octagon_formation_of_Chillicothe_and_New_ark_Earthworks

¹⁰ <https://etcsl.orinst.ox.ac.uk/section1/tr113.htm>

¹¹

https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1QnRXGf1kju3C_CZX06njKK-tnrGGjg5kOGkRAI-zSM/edit?usp=sharing

“Enuma Elish,”¹² and “Atrahasis,”¹³ as well as the sites at Maputo¹⁴, Bakoni, Gobekli Tepe, Peru, Sardinia, Moldova, Kentucky¹⁵, Utah, Columbia, and more, which attest to the death of the ancient dwarf star, Shamash, which (1) disintegrated first into proto-Saturn¹⁶ and Jupiter, and (2) then into Saturn, Neptune, and Jupiter, and (3) underwent a series of flares as they moved through a three-body-problem towards (4) a “awen” LaGrange Solution¹⁷ in the era known as the Golden Age of the Gods, with (5) Shamash/Osiris’ ‘intestines’ strewn throughout the “world’s tree” in the sky¹⁸.

Figure 2 - Columbia Rock Art, released 2020

It is safe to say that as Sol was not in the immediate sky but *on approach*¹⁹, giving Shamash the electrical stressing necessary to cause the bifurcation²⁰, that it in no way could have been associated with a so-called ‘micronova’. All magnetic excursions found in geology are mere imprinting of these radiative displays, recorded in countless rock motifs worldwide, and interpreted correctly by Peratt, Talbot, Cardona, Schoch, and many others *nearly correctly*. The

¹² <https://www.sacred-texts.com/ane/enuma.htm>

¹³ <https://geha.paginas.ufsc.br/files/2017/04/Atrahasis.pdf> or <https://eprints.soas.ac.uk/29625/1/10752597.pdf>

¹⁴ https://www.academia.edu/42656690/Secret_Held_in_Maputo

¹⁵ https://www.academia.edu/49456803/Trip_Report_Pebble_Beach_Red_River_Gorge

¹⁶ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Kff_ytg0-8w

¹⁷

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/354010454_Addendum_2_Megafauna_Extinction_Events_Update_to_the_Thunderbolt_Extinction_Model_the_Surprising_truth_of_the_Younger_Dryas_Event_that_Changes_Everything pp. 43-44

¹⁸ Ala “Hamlet’s Mill”

¹⁹ Apollo thus “grew like a baby” and Nibir/planet Uranus (not Ooranus the sky god) approached and Enlil beckoned it to be his son and it - Hades - remarks in the myths that his “mind was apart from Zeus”

²⁰ and/or LMH “lattice exclusion” as per Robitaille

YDE bifurcation of Shamash provides (1) ample material for Hudson Bay and Greenland strikes, (2) semi-directed energetics, (3) ages of chaos for climate changes and (4) atmospheric impulse to cause the event²¹, and later to melt the ice caps²², without the excessive kinetic power of a comet bolide/cryptoexplosive event. The crypto explosives were able to be, as I have proven, selective to megafauna especially via Step Potential²³, which Ben does not appear to be aware of at all.

It also matches not just some of the data, like in some Zamora-Carlson hypothesis²⁴, but covers all of Vogt's mythic data as well. Furthermore, it precludes (if there were some proof of a 12ky cycle, which there is not, that's an extrapolation of the 6kya event, doubled for convenience without precision!²⁵) any pole flip turnover predictability for **5,000 years**. He & Vogt cannot have it both ways. The magnetic field *appears to be accelerating* both in decrease in strength, and in motion. However, the result of that may not be to cause a flip, but to prevent it²⁶, since we now know that physical flips²⁷ are part and parcel of the Newtonian mechanics vis-a-vis conservation of angular momentum. We do not have enough clarity, even with the mantle extrusions, to divine the future from this.

The Current Sheet Debate

Furthermore, Ben has made a prediction that there is a series of flares, starting with Pluto²⁸, then Neptune, Uranus, etc. down the line that the Solar System is moving through a new current sheet²⁹ designated by the changing cosmic dust conditions as Sol proceeds through the precession cycle around SGR A*. This is a testable hypothesis (so: scientific³⁰). If he is right, then the data table should show flares on or around the dates. If I am right, and he is wrong, then not only have we missed the expected Saturn flare (if Jupiter happened), but the remainder are maybe not to be seen, or leastways in a linear fashion as he implies. I will not make the charge that he does this to sell tickets or reservations, although he adamantly reminds the audience that billionaires are fleeing to bunkers worldwide³¹.

²¹

https://www.academia.edu/37490311/Plasma_Petroglyphs_Plasmaglyphs_Earthworks_and_the_Megafau
[na_Extinction](#) p. 4, 104-110 (Part 4)

²² Ibid. ~6,000 to 12,000 Perattian Thunderbolts, pp. 115-118

²³ Ibid. pp. 120-125

²⁴ The Carolina Bays' chevrons alone prove Zamora wrong, but a more detailed description of his errors will be forthcoming. A treatment of the vector analysis is presented in ^

²⁵ Angular momentum must be conserved or you must point out a mechanism to change an orbit of a so called "cycle" by several hundred years!

²⁶ If the SSEC is analog, which is suspected, then it will respond instantly from a geological perspective to any and all changing variables in a cosmic rearrangement "dance" of magnetism and electricity. Electricity leads the dance, they are 90 degrees out of phase with one another. See "Electric Currents in Geospace and Beyond," Wiley, 2017

²⁷ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1VPfZ_XzisU

²⁸ 2016, way too early, https://chandra.harvard.edu/press/16_releases/press_091416.html

²⁹ <https://phys.org/news/2012-08-thin-current-sheets-space-action.html> and
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/1811.08563.pdf>

³⁰ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/home/standards>

³¹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=A1OcM87qEBs>

Table 1³²

Flare	Date	Distance (AU)	Rel. Velocity		Prediction Date
Neptune	8/15/2020	10.9	0.04801762115		
Uranus	3/30/2021	9.6	0.05748502994	19.72%	
Saturn		4.4			10/15/2021
Jupiter	9/13/2021	3.7			1/15/2022
Mars	11/5/2021	0.5			4/2/2022
Earth	11/12/2021				4/13/2022

As we can see, if Jupiter flared, then there was a relative velocity increase of Sol through the cosmos of 19.7%. How does he explain this without electricity?

If we use a constant velocity then we should expect a flare at the dates on the right. If we assume constant acceleration, then Mars should flare by ~11/5/21, and Earth by ~11/21/21.

So, we shall see what we see, and I am not above the possibility of this scientific hypothesis to be proven correct. The pseudoscience I firmly reject in light of all of the physical evidence, both in rock art, earthwork, petroglyphs, and in geological and astronomical data. I firmly stand by my treatise and the two addendums, which show that Dr. Peratt *and* Wal Thornhill are essentially correct, and Vogt is wrong³³.

The main mechanism of delivery of energy are Birkeland Currents³⁴/"flux ropes"³⁵, but not only they. It is also important to note that there is no such thing as magnetic disconnect or "frozen in fields,"³⁶ these are just models for the actual data.³⁷

I absolutely detest the implication that Mr. Davidson represents the PEMC or plasma cosmology, in his behavior towards the mainstream, in misleading his audience with pseudoscience such as *a priori* knowledge. I challenge him to do better, and pray for his reeling in of the ego lest he continue to misrepresent those who came before us³⁸ and all the rest of current altstream researchers who already struggle against the Shermers and "professor" Dave's of the world, and of course paid media propagandists (such as Vice and Nature).

Thank you,
Sf. R. Careaga

³² Credit: author,
<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1dqVRar0VZed5TrMBdEmmIYA1v8ax-MPOX8VlpzAZdoQ/edit?usp=sharing>

³³ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mra-AmaG33c>

³⁴

https://www.portal.uni-koeln.de/9015.html?&L=1&tx_news_pi1%5Bcontroller%5D=News&tx_news_pi1%5Baction%5D=detail&tx_news_pi1%5Bnews%5D=5413&cHash=b1ae76d85b1a6be1bf3b80dd9cc77dea

³⁵ https://www.nasa.gov/multimedia/imagegallery/image_feature_2069.html

³⁶ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ILUmJmDi6uM>

³⁷

<https://www.nasa.gov/feature/goddard/2018/nasa-spacecraft-discovers-new-magnetic-process-in-turbulent-space>

³⁸ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/eu-general/giants-of-eu-history>

Figure 3 - Magnetic Turbulence in Space ([gif](#)); credit: NASA³⁹

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https://www.nasa.gov/sites/default/files/styles/ubernode_alt_horiz/public/thumbnails/image/bannerturbulence.gif